

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4567822>

УДК 616-006.04

STATISTICS OF CANCER CASES OF THE THYROID GLAND AMONG CHILDREN AND TEENAGERS IN REPUBLIC OF BELARUS DURING THE POST-CHERNOBYL PERIOD

A.S. Aleksandrovich,

PhD in Medical sciences

T.I. Zimatkina,

PhD in Biological sciences, Associate Professor,

Grodno state medical university,

Republic of Belarus, Grodno

Abstract: Dynamics of cancer cases of a thyroid gland among children and teenagers during 1986-2014 is studied. It is established that in Republic of Belarus cancer of a thyroid gland the people who received an exposure dose at children's age mainly are ill. The cancer cases of a thyroid gland at such people have wavy character. For the analyzed period the incidence at first increased during the period from 1989 to 1990 and the peak of incidence at children fell on 1995, and since 2001 (the peak of incidence at teenagers) began to decrease.

Keywords: thyroid gland, malignant new growths, children, teenagers

АНАЛИЗ СТАТИСТИКИ ЗАБОЛЕВАЕМОСТИ РАКОМ ЩИТОВИДНОЙ ЖЕЛЕЗЫ СРЕДИ ДЕТЕЙ И ПОДРОСТКОВ В РЕСПУБЛИКЕ БЕЛАРУСЬ В ПОСТЧЕРНОБЫЛЬСКИЙ ПЕРИОД

А.С. Александрович,

к.м.н.

Т.И. Зиматкина,

к.б.н., доц.,

Гродненский государственный медицинский университет,

Республика Беларусь, г. Гродно

Аннотация: Изучена динамика заболеваемости раком щитовидной железы среди детей и подростков за период 1986-2014 гг. Установлено, что в Республике Беларусь рак щитовидной железы преимущественно болеют люди, получившие дозу облучения в детском возрасте. Заболеваемость раком щитовидной железы у таких людей носит волнообразный характер. За

анализируемый период заболеваемость сначала возрастала в период с 1989 по 1990 г. и пик заболеваемости у детей пришёлся на 1995 г., а с 2001 г. (пик заболеваемости у подростков) начала уменьшаться.

Ключевые слова: щитовидная железа, злокачественные новообразования, дети, подростки

Relevance. On modern representations, cancer of a thyroid gland (CTG) are manifestations of malignant new growths, united the general localization heterogeneous on a range, which meet at female persons more often, mainly in age group 15 years are more senior [1-3].

In the territory of Republic of Belarus (RB) two etiologic CTG forms – sporadic and radiogenic, caused by incorporation of isotopes of iodine during the post-Chernobyl period meet. The last option is most widespread in the southern regions of RB since 1992. Till 1990 CTG was a rare oncological disease. Since the beginning of the 1990th years, the steady growth of incidence in all age groups is noted, especially high growth of incidence of CTG is observed at children and teenagers [4-8].

The purpose – to study dynamics of cancer cases of a thyroid gland among children and teenagers during 1986-2014.

Materials and methods. As material for this research served data of Belarusian Cantser-registr for 1986-2014 and the materials presented in references. In work used a method of comparative analysis.

Results and their discussion. As a result of the Chernobyl accident radio iodine (first of all iodine-131) was one of the main sources of radiation of the population which influenced first of all a thyroid gland. Children and teenagers, especially children under 7 years were the most irradiated residents of Belarus. When studying territorial spread of a thyroid carcinoma to RB significant differences in its prevalence are noted. First place on the frequency of developing of cancer of this localization was won by Minsk, on the last place there were Grodno and Brest regions. In 20 years (1965-1985) this tumor was revealed only at 21 children. At the same time, the risk to ache was minimum in an age interval of 15-29 years.

During the postemergency period, the situation sharply changed. In 1990, i.e. on the fifth year after accident, the standardized incidence indicator in the Gomel region reached level 3.7 (± 0.96), i.e. 106 cases of incidence. Sharp rise in incidence in the area is registered in 1991 that made 8.47 (± 1.43). During 1986-1994 in the republic, 333 children and 81 teenagers got sick. From among sick children 180 at the time of accident lived in the Gomel region, 74 – in Brest, on 19 – in Grodno and Minsk, 6 – in Vitebsk, 16 – in Mogilev, 18 – in Minsk, 1 child moved from Pripyat (Ukraine). The analysis of these data demonstrates that the

Gomel region surpasses in risk of incidence of CTG Vitebsk by 30 times. The factor of migration led to some decrease in an indicator of incidence in the Gomel and Brest regions and, on the contrary, to significant increase it in Minsk and the Minsk region (24 cases of diseases of CTG are registered in Minsk and 27 – in the Minsk region).

During 1977-1985 at the age of 0-14 years among children and male teenagers the indicator of incidence of CTG (on 100,000 population) was 0.03 ± 0.02 , and among a female 0.1 ± 0.02 . Thus, the indicator of prevalence of this ZN at children and female teenagers is about 3.33 times higher, than at a male. In the period of 1986-1994 among children and male teenagers, the indicator of incidence of CTG (on 100,000 population) was 1.2 ± 0.36 , among a female 2.0 ± 0.67 . From this, it follows that the incidence indicator at a female approximately by 1.67 times exceeds an indicator at a male. Therefore, during the postemergency period the incidence of CTG at children and female teenagers at the age of 0-14 years increased by 20 times in comparison with the before accident period. Sharp growth of number of patients with tireoid cancer of children began in 1990, continued 6 years and reached peak (90 cases) in 1995. In the Gomel region the incidence of CTG among children and female teenagers at the age of 0-14 years in the period of 1977-1985 was 0.1 ± 0.07 , and in the period of 1986-1994 – 6.0 ± 2.18 . The obtained data demonstrate that during the postemergency period incidence of CTG at children and female teenagers increased by 60 times in comparison with the before accident period. Mortality from CTG practically did not change.

In 1995 the incidence of CTG among children in age group of 0-14 years was 3.29 ± 0.34 , in 1999 1.77 ± 0.25 . The peak of incidence in this interval fell on 1995 – 90 cases. Thus, the incidence in this period gradually decreased by 54 %. At teenagers, the noticeable growth of cases of cancer began in 1997 and since then annually increased.

In 2000 the incidence of CTG among children in age group of 0-14 years was 1.21 ± 0.21 , and in 2005 0.81 ± 0.22 . The peak of incidence in this interval fell on 2000. The incidence in this interval decreases by 67 %. In 2001 in age group of 15-19 years the peak of incidence of CTG made 10:100,000. It follows from this that, since 1994, the quantity of cases of incidence of CTG moderately decreases. And in the Gomel region the incidence indicator on 100,000 in 2000 was at children 5.4, at teenagers – 33.7.

In 2006 the incidence of CTG among children in age group of 0-14 years was 0.41, in 2010 – 0.78. The peak of incidence of CTG fell on 2010. Proceeding from these data, it is visible that the number of cases of diseases in 2010 gradually increased by 1.9 times. In 2006 the incidence of CTG among teenagers in age group of 15-19 years was 2.52, in 2010 – 3.67. The peak was observed in 2009 and made 4.36.

In 2011 the incidence of CTG among children in age group of 0-14 years was 0.21, in 2014 – 0.70. The peak of incidence of CTG fell on 2012 and 2014 – 0.70. In 2011 in age group of 15-19 years the incidence of CTG among teenagers was 4.41, in 2014 – 5.10. The peak is registered in 2014. Thus, the incidence among teenagers increased by 1.16 times.

Conclusion. During work it is established, in RB CTG the people who received a radiation dose at children's age mainly are ill. The incidence at such people has wavy character. For the analyzed period the incidence of CTG at first increased during the period from 1989 to 1990 and the peak of incidence at children fell on 1995, and since 2001 (the peak of incidence at teenagers) began to decrease.

References

[1] Demidchik E.P. Thyroid cancer in children. / E.P. Demidchik, Yu.E. Demidchik, V.Ya. Rebeco. // Medical aspects of radioactive impact on the population living in the contaminated area after the accident at the Chernobyl nuclear power plant. – Gomel, 1994. 43-44 pp.

[2] Okeanov A.E. The incidence of thyroid cancer in the Republic of Belarus. / A.E. Okeanov, E.P. Demidchik, M.A. Ankudovich. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/zabolevaemost-rakom-schitovidnoy-zhelezzy-v-respublike-belarus>. (дата обращения: 16.01.2021).

[3] Savva N.N. Malignant neoplasms in children of the Republic of Belarus: Morbidity, survival, mortality and palliative care. / N.N. Savva, A.A. Zborovskaya, O. V. Aleinikov. – Minsk: GU RNMB, 2008. 184 p.

[4] Kunitskaya S.V. The incidence of thyroid cancer in the Republic of Belarus from 2005 to 2014. / S.V. Kunitskaya, V.Yu. Demidchik, A.D. Getmanova. // Modern problems of public health and health care. – Grodno, 2016. 153-157 pp.

[5] Demidchik V.Yu. Thyroid cancer statistics in the Republic of Belarus. / V.Yu. Demidchik, I.A. Savateev. // Actual problems of modern medicine and pharmacy 2015: collection of articles. materials 69th scientific-practical. conf. students and young scientists from intern. participation: at 2 pm / Belarusian. state honey. un-t; ed. O.K. Kulagi, E.V. Barkovsky. – Minsk: BSMU, 2015. Part 2. 141-144 pp.

[6] Medical consequences of the Chernobyl accident and special health programs: report of the expert group «Health» of the UN Chernobyl Forum, Geneva, 2006. / under the editorship of J. Carr [and others]. – Geneva, 2006. 27-65 pp.

[7] Petrovich S.V. Epidemiology of malignant neoplasms in children. / S.V. Petrovich, O.V. Aleinikov. – Minsk: Bel. Navuka, 2004. 170 p.

[8] Malignant neoplasms in Belarus 1998-2007. / S.M. Polyakov, L.F. Levin, N.G. Shebeko; ed. A.A. Grakovich, I.V. Zalutsky. – Minsk: RSPC M, 2008. 197 p.

© A.S. Aleksandrovich, T.I. Zimatkina, 2021

Поступила в редакцию 14.01.2021

Принята к публикации 15.01.2021

Для цитирования:

Aleksandrovich A.S., Zimatkina T.I. Statistics of cancer cases of the thyroid gland among children and teenagers in republic of belarus during the post-chernobyl period // Инновационные научные исследования : сетевой журнал. 2021. № 1-2(3). С. 142-146. URL: <https://ip-journal.ru/>